

Image of Navoi in Oibek's "Navoi"

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Annotation: This article discusses the novel "Navoi" by Oybek. The history of writing the novel and its achievements, the image of Navoi in the novel and his characteristics are covered.

Key words: Oybek's novel "Navoi", Alisher Navoi, textile images, historical images, Jami and Navoi, nationalist poet, lifelong work. Fiction, artistic work is such a blessing that centuries-long miracles are stored in them, heroes full of love and knowledge of language are always alive. Periods pass, each of them creates a genius and leaves his knowledge and creativity to the next generation. XIV- XV centuries occupy a special place in the history of our country. During these centuries, majestic structures - architectural monuments - were built, which have been the pride of the East until now. Literature, art and science developed widely. Alisher Navoi's great works were created as a symbol and result of this development. Navoi was not only a great poet, but also had a great influence on the social, economic, cultural and educational life of the 15th century. The glimmer of Navoi's creativity has reached us and is spreading light to our hearts. It is not surprising that Ustoz Oybek wanted to introduce Navoi, who is considered the genius of the past centuries, to us through his novel "Navoi". The main goal of Ustoz Oibek is to create the image of Navoi as a great man, poet and statesman. In order to create the image of Oybek Navoi as a humanitarian poet and statesman, he included the image of historical figures and artistic textile images in the work. These are, first of all, Navoi's student Sultanmurad, his friend Arslanqul and his lover Dildar. They participate in the events of the novel as representatives of ordinary people and help reveal the image of Navoi as a great person, poet and statesman. Dozens of heroes such as Husayn Boygaro, Jami, Behzod, Nizamulmulk, and Majididdin entered Oibek's work directly from the universalconference.us pages of history. The author's novel depicts various events typical for the life of the 15th century and creates colorful images. The reality of life is masterfully transformed into an artistic reality. In this, the writer effectively used psychological analysis, language capabilities, including the art of giving each character's unique character and individual language. Accordingly, all characters in the novel are distinguished from each other by their character and individual language and attention. It must be decorated with freshness, imbued with the spirit

of the era. The life of the period is described in the work, the language characteristics of the speech of the people of that period should also be reflected. In this respect, the language of the novel "Navoi" is instructive. As Hamil Yaqubov, a scholar of Oybek studies, rightly noted: "Navoi" novel plays an important role in the formation of the language of Uzbek historical novels. The language of the work has become one of the examples of creating a living language of the past, in which the language of historical heroes who lived five hundred years ago was revived to be understandable to modern readers. Oybek correctly solved this difficult task facing the Roman language. The success of the writer was that he did not set a sharp boundary between the speech of the characters and the speech of the author and combined the historical and modern speech. He preserved the color of the literary language of the Navoi era in the speech of individuals, stylized some grammatical and morphological forms, and subjected them to the basic rules specific to the current stage of development of the Uzbek literary language, bringing it as close as possible to the understanding of the modern reader. But the fact is that the language of the author could not be completely separated from the language of the characters and enriched with the innovations of today's vocabulary. Therefore, the writer tried to preserve the stylistic unity between the language of the author and the language of the characters, appropriately used Arabic, Tajik and archaic words that are out of use now»¹. These indicate that the image of Navoi is brought to the level that the universalconference.us reader understands, his intellect accepts, and he loves and respects. In general, it is necessary to have enough knowledge to understand and enjoy the samples of Navoi's creativity: his epics with mysticism, his ghazals that sing of divine love, and these aspects are a certain distance between the ordinary reader and Navoi. creates. Ustoz Oybek shortened this distance a little, that is, he was able to convey all the qualities of Navoi to the common reader in simple language. In the novel, as well as the language of the characters, the author's speech is made with great skill. In the work, Oybek effectively used the riches of the living folk language: folk proverbs, wise sayings and figurative expressions, as well as figurative tools such as simile, qualification, revitalization, exaggeration, metaphor. Oybek propagated patriotism, humanity, heroism and hatred of evil based on reflecting the reality of the past, creating the image of the great historical figure Alisher Navoi, depicting his boundless love for the Motherland and the people, which fully corresponded to the requirements of the wartime. Navoi admonished his friends: "...we must strive to avoid every kind of calamity... It is our duty to be selfless for the health of the Blessed Motherland and the nation." I wish you to be loyal to each other, to the state, to the country, with love. "Loyalty and love are great

powers," he says. According to the poet and translator A. Naumov, Aibek spoke to him about the history of the creation of the novel "Navoi" and said to him: "Before writing, I saw my heroes clearly, in my mind, they grew from the seeds once thrown into the plow of history. "It was as if they had come out," he said. This opinion of the writer applies not only to historical figures, but also to textile images. According to the same interlocutor, Oibek told him the following words: "On my desk lay a map of Herat in the middle ages, which I had drawn myself. I used to go to sleep in Herat and wake up in Herat, only at night I would dream of Tashkent where I live". stands out. In the example of Oybek's work, modernity and historicity, tradition and innovation, conflict and character, vitality and artistic texture, form and content, specific features of lyrical, epic and lyric- universalconference.us epic genres, common and different aspects between them. you can think about it. In Matyoqub Koshjanov's book "Oibek's skill" the literary skill is analyzed in connection with the process of creative development and issues of unique style. In particular, the formation of the main characters in Oybek's works is carefully covered, and it is mentioned that the relationship between subject and composition, form and content is delicately connected. Of course, the novel "Navoiy" is a vivid example of such skills. In the novel, Aybek used the image of Navoiy's attitude to the Turkish language and literature to create the image of a great poet. As Haqqani describes in the novel, Navoi loves his mother tongue, Turkish, with all his heart. But in the novel, Alisher Navoi rightly points out that he did not discriminate against other languages. In the novel, Navoi objected to the poet Binoy: "We have never denied the power and importance of the Persian language, the beauty and virtue of the works in that language. We have been writing in Persian since childhood. But the advantage of our language is a great truth for us. We have cherished this love of truth in our hearts, and we will keep this love until we die! We have clans, clans and regions that fill cities, villages, deserts and mountains, and they have their own pleasure and understanding. Let us think of the pleasure and nature of our country and write in its own language so that its heart is filled with the flowers of thought. Let's sing praises with Turkish words, let the hearts of the people rise. Let our country enjoy the flower of words along with other countries" ⁴, he says. The author describes with fascination that Jami and Navoi are each other's teacher and student. Simple human relationships between lifetimes are also expressed with sincerity. Before leaving for Marv, Navoi visits Jami with the intention of saying goodbye: "Jami welcomes him enthusiastically as always. The still great old man (Jomjy) who was sitting Navoi smiled gently and said with his own gentleness: "Will you now turn our eyes to Marv?" ⁵ - he said. From this conversation, we can feel the sincerity

between the two geniuses, the delicacy and sophistication of the conversation. Aibek skillfully universalconference.us showed the creative process of the poet . He tried to describe Navoi's hardships in the process of writing "Khamasa" , as well as how his other works came to the world. Navoi's attitude towards religion is also reflected in the work. The dream of the great thinker to go on pilgrimage is so beautifully expressed in the work that you will be surprised to read it, but this dream remains a dream for Navoi. Before that , the appointment of the poet as the governor of Astrabad caused him to distance himself from his friends, scientists , and homesickness. At that time, Navoi feels longing and writes the following rubai: A stranger in a foreign country cannot be happy, El anga shafigu cannot be kind, A golden cage cannot be filled with a red flower, A nightingale cannot be as thorny as a thorn. .In the play, he showed true patriotism through the character of Oybek Navoi. In addition, the injustices that occurred in Herat and Khurasan during the time of the Timurid prince Husayn Baigaro, the conflicts between father and son, the murder of Momin Mirza, the struggle for the crown throne, and the relentless search for the betterment of the people are clearly described. . Navoi's glorification of human qualities, loyalty to values, and constant concern for the country deserve praise. In the work, the characteristics of Navoi's character are manifested in the qualities of honesty, determination and nobility. In the image of Navoi, we can see the greatest qualities, his patriotism, always thinking of the people's interests in all parts of the work. In particular, his hard work for the motherland and its prosperity is worthy of praise. The fact that he began to write a novel with serious preparation testifies to the fact that he clearly imagined the forces that make up the conflict of the work and the persons who represent these forces. In conclusion, The novel "Navoi" is an excellent example of Uzbek novelism and a great achievement. This novel has been translated into Russian, English, Ukrainian, German, Belorussian, Kazakh, Turkmen, Azerbaijani, Tajik, Arabic, Persian, Estonian, Latvian and Chinese languages of the world and has been liked by readers everywhere. The image of Navoi, the example of the sun, enlightened the heart of teacher Oybek universalconference.us and gave love . The restrained way of examples of classical works gives the reader a special pleasure. Especially, the richness and beauty of the language of the work, the presence of beautiful allusions between every two sentences gives inspiration along with pleasure . Master Oybek skillfully connected the changes in the mental state of the characters with the scenery of nature. Every simile found in the work is wrapped in a thread of elegance. Of course, this can be attributed to the charm of the main character's work. The writer brings Navoi into the work at the stage of maturity, at the time when he has seen the ups and downs,

black and white of life . This is because he aims to portray Aibek in the reader's imagination as a noble, loved by friends and people, patron of creative people, fair in everything, possessing a delicate heart. From the work, we can know that Navoi has a great talent. Navoi's knowledge in this field is evidenced by his constant contact with the masters of various fine creative paths, such as the scientist Sultanmurad, the artist Kamoliddin Behzod, the calligrapher Sultanali Mashhadi, the historian grandfather and grandsons - Mirkhond and Khondamir. From the language of the heroes of the work, Zayniddin and Sultanmurad: "Alisher is a person with extensive knowledge in all areas of human thought . From history, philosophy, logic to tyranny, musicality, he did not leave any field", "Some statuses created for his skill in music are evidence; "He considers ignorance of music to be a great defect for a poet"6 is not an exaggeration, it is a description of a talent that amazes a person. He is a great person who showed great courage for the formation of the Turkish language as a literary language and created an inexhaustible treasure in the Turkish language . In fact, the novel "Navoi" has its artistic-aesthetic value, content-essence, familiarity with artistic-descriptive tools, consistency of events, the fact that it can be a mirror of real reality, the characters interact with each other, that is, the whole It is a work worthy of high praise and recognition due to the combination of religious and historical images. That is why this century has not lost its value, and will not lose it. Because a truly artistic work of art never universalconference.us dies. People will not forget such works. This novel by Oybek, who was able to beautifully describe the image of Navoi, who is considered a bright figure and a great thinker in Uzbek classic literature, will live forever with the rare examples of Alisher Navoi's work. When you look at the novel , the bright figure of the noble, temperamental poet looks at you lovingly from the pages. REFERENCES 1. Mirzayev S. Uzbek literature of the 20th century . T-2004 2. Umarov H. Literary theory. T-2004 3. Boboyev T. Basics of literary studies. T-2002 4. Oybek . Navoi's novel. T-1963 5. Oybek. Navoi's novel. T-1963 6. Journal of Uzbek language and literature. Issues of 2005 7. Uzbek national encyclopedia. T-2000, volume 5. 8. Sadiq S. New Uzbek literature. Text of lectures, T-1999